

STRUCTURE AND ULTIMATE PHYSICO-MECHANICAL PROPERTIES
OF REINFORCING POLYMER MATERIALS (FIBRES, FILMS AND WHISKERS)

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The essential problem of physical chemistry and technology of oriented polymer materials, used for reinforcement consists in the further improvement of their physico-mechanical properties by means of creating maximum uniform and low-defective structures with high orientation.

In this connection the properties, indicating the ultimate values of physico-mechanical characteristics of linear and laminated oriented polymer structures, are of great theoretic and practical importance: theoretic and obtainable strength, theoretic modulus of elasticity etc., that is those limits that can be obtained.

The calculations of these indices are given both for conventional types of polymers and for new ones of organic and inorganic polymer structures including aromatic parapolyamides, graphite, hexagonal boron nitride and silicon carbide.

The estimate of the theoretic strength of the oriented polymers has been made on the basis of regularities of total deformation of chains and strength temperature-time dependence. It is shown that the theoretic strength can be realized only at the temperature of absolute zero and it ranges for different linear polymers from 800 to 3100 kg/mm² and for laminated structures (graphite) to 14000 kg/mm².

The concept of obtainable strength as a strength of ideal polymer structure at given temperature-time conditions of deformation has been introduced.

The obtainable strength is shown to be of the order of 1/6-1/3 of the theoretic strength value for the maximum oriented materials on the basis of linear polymers at 20°C and the time of deformation nearly 10 sec. and that it 2-5 times exceeds the obtained experimental strength data for different polymers.

Elastic properties of linear and laminated polymer structures have been considered and the ultimate moduli of elasticity of oriented polymers have been estimated (by three independent methods).

The values of ultimate moduli of elasticity of oriented linear structures are 20000-25000 kg/mm² and the moduli of elasticity of laminated structures

(graphite, hexagonal boron nitride and silicon carbide) are 80000-110000 kg/mm².

The relationship between theoretic and maximum obtained moduli for different polymers has been considered.

The ultimate mechanical properties of the new chain carbon polymer-carbine have been estimated.

It is shown that carbine can have probably the highest values of strength and elasticity modulus as compared to all kinds of oriented polymer materials ($\sigma_{\text{theor.}} \approx 22000-23000 \text{ kg/mm}^2$; $E_{\text{abt}} \approx 19000-20000 \text{ kg/mm}^2$; $E_{\text{theor}} \approx 180000 \text{ kg/mm}^2$).

The results of calculation of ultimate heat-resistance of chain and laminated structures with the used temperature-time dependence of strength are given.

The difference between available and obtainable physico-mechanical properties of oriented polymers at present is the result of imperfection of their structure, which is heterogeneous and defective on different levels: molecular, supermolecular and macrolevel.

The influence of chemical and conformal heterogeneity of molecular structure and the main indices of supermolecular structure (density, packing, orientation, peculiarities of amorphous crystalline structure) on the level of obtainable mechanical properties of oriented polymers have been evaluated.

Rather important influence of macrostructure of polymers on mechanical properties has also been considered.

It should be stressed the high anisotropy of properties of oriented linear polymers which sometimes negatively influence on their appliance as reinforcing materials.

Some requirements are given to the structure and properties of polymers for the production of high strength and high-modulus reinforcing materials.

SESSION 2:
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